

EFFECTIVENESS OF THINK-PAIR-SHARE STRATEGY ON EFL KERALA LEARNERS IN VOCABULARY ACHIEVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study employed a quasi-experimental design to examine the impact of the Think-Pair-Share (TPS) strategy on the vocabulary achievement of 8th English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners in Kerala. It also explored learners' perceptions of the values of practicing the TPS strategy. The research was conducted during the 2023 - 2024 academic year and involved two groups: a control group and an experimental group. Data collection was carried out using a vocabulary test and a student perception questionnaire. Both groups underwent pretesting to evaluate their vocabulary levels and ensure comparability. Over four weeks, the experimental group participated in TPS-based activities, while the control group was taught using traditional methods. After treatment the attitude towards TPS was assessed for experimental group by student perception questionnaire. Mean, Standard Deviation, Paired Sample T- Test and Independent Sample T- Test were the statistical techniques used for the study. The data were analysed using SPSS. The findings indicated that the experimental group significantly outperformed the control group in vocabulary achievement. Moreover, students expressed positive attitudes toward the implementation of the TPS strategy. Thus, the study suggests introducing TPS as an effective method for Kerala learners.

Keywords: Think-Pair-Share strategy (TPS), English as a Foreign Language (EFL), Vocabulary Achievement and Traditional Methods

Introduction

English has become one of the most widely spoken languages worldwide, making its teaching and learning a priority in many countries, including Oman. In the Omani education system, English is recognized as a vital tool for communication and progress (Al-Habsi et al., 2022). To master English, individuals must develop proficiency in its core skills: reading,

listening, speaking, and writing. Among these, vocabulary forms the foundation of effective language learning and use (Ihsan, 2019; Schmitt, 2000; Al Qasmi et al., 2022). Rivers (1981) underscored the pivotal role of vocabulary in language acquisition, calling it the dynamic centre of communication and learning. As such, employing varied and effective strategies to enhance vocabulary development is essential. Studies in Oman have highlighted the significant challenges students face in acquiring vocabulary, particularly in reading and writing (Seyabi & Tuzlukova, 2015). Research by Al-Maawaliya (2008) and Al Qasmi et al. (2022) revealed that limited vocabulary knowledge hinders students' ability to communicate effectively in English, negatively affecting their overall proficiency and attitudes toward the language. Al-Saadi (2021) discovered that Omani elementary students struggle with reading fluency and comprehension, often reading slowly and with hesitation. Similarly, Al-Kharusi (2014) noted that many students read in a disjointed, word-by-word manner due to limited vocabulary and poor word recognition skills. These challenges often lead to reduced motivation to learn English. Without a strong vocabulary foundation, learning a foreign language becomes particularly difficult.

The importance of vocabulary in language learning, a critical question arises: which teaching strategies most effectively build vocabulary knowledge? Extensive research on EFL teaching highlights the Think-Pair-Share (TPS) strategy as a highly effective approach for enhancing English language skills (Abrane et al., 2019; Ihsan, 2019; Aisyiah, 2022). Amelia (2016) further emphasized that TPS fosters improved reading and vocabulary outcomes by encouraging active student participation in the learning process.

This study seeks to address the following research questions:

- Does the implementation of the TPS strategy lead to statistically significant differences in vocabulary achievement between the experimental and control groups?
- What are students' perceptions of the TPS strategy as part of their learning experience?

METHOD

Design

The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design, specifically the non-equivalent control group design, to investigate the research questions. As noted by Maciejewski (2020), this type of design assesses the impact of a specific intervention on predetermined participants. In this study, two pre-existing groups were selected: one experimental group and one control group. The experimental group received the Think-Pair-Share (TPS) intervention, while the control group was taught using traditional methods. Both groups underwent pretests and post-tests. The

intervention's effectiveness was evaluated by comparing the post-test results of the two groups. To ensure the accurate implementation of the TPS strategy, the researcher conducted the sessions for the experimental group directly.

Population and Sample

The research focused on 8th std students in Kerala. A convenience sample was drawn from two intact eighth-grade classes (N = 66) at Govt school in Kerala. The school offers students five English lessons per week. The choice of participants was based on the school's readiness to participate in the research. The two selected classes, each with 33 female students aged between 13 and 14, were chosen due to their similar academic performance in the previous term English course.

Instruments

Two primary instruments were utilized to collect data: a vocabulary test and a questionnaire.

Pretest/Post-test

The vocabulary test was administered as both a pretest and a post-test to measure the impact of the TPS strategy on students' vocabulary acquisition. It comprised three sections:

- Completing a text by selecting the correct option.
- Fill in sentences with appropriate words.
- Matching pictures to their corresponding words.

The test items were adapted from assessments provided by the SCERT Text book and were aligned with the topics covered in Unit Three of the eighth-grade textbook to ensure their suitability for students' language proficiency levels. The pretest was conducted before the intervention, and the post-test followed afterwards. Pretest results showed no significant differences between the two groups, confirming their equivalency at the study's outset. To evaluate the test's reliability, a pilot study was conducted with 28 eighth-grade students. Cronbach's alpha was calculated to assess internal consistency, producing a value of 0.761, indicating a strong correlation among test items.

The Questionnaire

A questionnaire was administered to the experimental group to explore their attitude towards TPS strategy. It included 16 statements across four dimensions: engagement and enjoyment, vocabulary development, communication and collaboration, and academic

performance. Responses were collected using a five-point Likert scale (5 = Strongly agree to 1 = Strongly disagree). To ensure reliability, the questionnaire was piloted with 16 eighth-grade students, achieving a Cronbach's alpha of .744, indicating strong internal consistency.

Reliability and Validity of the Instruments

Cronbach's alpha was used to measure internal consistency. The pretest and post-test showed a reliability coefficient of 0.817, while the questionnaire recorded 0.813, both indicating strong item correlations. For validity, educational experts reviewed the instruments for relevance, clarity, and suitability, and their feedback was incorporated into modifications.

The TPS Intervention

The TPS strategy was implemented with the experimental group over four weeks in 10 sessions. Activities aligned with the eighth-grade curriculum included tasks adapted from class resources and newly designed ones, reviewed by English teachers for clarity and relevance.

The intervention followed three phases: independent thinking on prompts, peer discussion of ideas, and group presentations. The teacher facilitated the process and provided feedback to enhance vocabulary.

Procedures

The study was conducted during the first semester of the 2023/2024 academic year, spanning November.

Two classes were selected after consulting teachers to ensure homogeneity. Consent was obtained from students and the principal.

A pretest was administered to measure vocabulary achievement and confirm group equivalence. Students were informed about the test's purpose, and 40 minutes were allocated for completion. Pretest results were analysed using an independent samples t-test to compare the experimental and control groups.

Data Analysis

Various statistical techniques were employed to analyse the data. An independent samples t-test was used to identify differences between the control and experimental groups in pretests and post-tests. A paired samples t-test was conducted to compare the experimental group's pre- and post-test mean scores. The questionnaire data were analysed using descriptive statistics with the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

Table 1

Experimental and Control Groups' Independent Sample T-Test Scores in the
Vocabulary Pretest

Group	N	Df	M	SD	T-value	Sig (2-tailed)
Control	33	64	10.8	4.43	0.000	1.000
Experimental			10.8	3.63		

The control and experimental groups had identical mean scores of 10.8 on the pretest, with standard deviations of 4.43 and 3.63, respectively. The t-value was 0.000, and the p-value (Sig, 2-tailed) was 1.000, indicating no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p > .05$). This confirmed their equivalence in vocabulary achievement before the intervention, suggesting that any post-treatment differences could be attributed to the TPS strategy. After the treatment, both groups underwent post-testing following the same procedures as the pretest. Additionally, the experimental group completed a questionnaire during a session to share their perceptions of the TPS strategy.

Results and Discussion

The findings were structured according to the research questions.

Research Question One

An independent samples t-test was performed to compare the post-test results of the control and experimental groups, evaluating the impact of the TPS strategy on EFL Kerala readers learners' vocabulary achievement.

Table 2.

Control and Experimental Groups' Independent Sample T-test Scores in the Vocabulary Achievement Posttest

Groups	N	M	SD	T-value	P
Control	33	11.1	4.1	2.43	.018
Experimental	33	13.5	3.8		

The control group (N = 33) had a mean score of 11.1 (SD = 4.1), while the experimental group (N = 33) achieved a higher mean of 13.5 (SD = 3.8). The t-value was 2.43 with a p-value of .018, indicating that the experimental group's vocabulary achievement was significantly better than the control group's at the .05 significance level. This demonstrates the positive impact of the TPS strategy on the experimental group.

The findings suggest that the experimental group built a stronger vocabulary. TPS encourages independent reflection, peer interaction, and collaborative learning, which collectively enhance vocabulary retention and growth. This strategy also boosts confidence and active participation, as highlighted by Abrane et al. (2019) and Amelia (2016). Furthermore, TPS incorporates cognitive processes such as independent thinking, idea exchange, and group discussions, which strengthen memory and embed new words more effectively, as noted by Raba (2017).

A paired sample t-test was also conducted to compare the experimental group's pretest and post test scores, further evaluating the impact of TPS strategy. Table 3 presents these findings.

Table 3.

Experimental Group's Paired Sample T-test Scores in the Vocabulary Achievement Pretest

Test	M	SD	T-value	P
Pretest	10.8	3.6	5.41	.000
Posttest	13.5	3.8		

The pretest mean score of the experimental group was 10.8 (SD = 3.6), which increased to 13.5 (SD = 3.8) in the posttest. The t-value was 5.41 with a p-value of .000, indicating a statistically significant improvement in vocabulary achievement after implementing the TPS strategy. This demonstrates the TPS strategy's positive effect on the experimental group's performance.

For Research Question Two, a questionnaire was used to gather the attitude of experimental group towards TPS strategy. The questionnaire included 16 items across four dimensions: engagement and enjoyment, vocabulary development, communication and collaboration, and academic performance.

Table 4

Mean and standard deviation for all dimensions.

Dimension	M	SD
Engagement and enjoyment	4.5	.372
Vocabulary development	4.4	.442
Communication and collaboration	4.4	.594
Academic performance	4.3	.563
Overall	4.4	.361

The overall mean score of 4.4 with a low standard deviation of 0.361 reflected a consistently positive impact across all dimensions. Participants rated the strategy highest for engagement and enjoyment (M = 4.5), followed closely by vocabulary development (M = 4.4), communication and collaboration (M = 4.4), and academic performance (M = 4.3). These results highlight the TPS strategy's broad and positive influence on the learning experience. The questionnaire results were further detailed in Tables 5 to 8, which presented the means and standard deviations for each item within the four dimensions.

Table 5.
Descriptive Statistics for the Experimental Group's Responses in the Engagement and
Enjoyment Dimension

Item	M	SD
1.I enjoyed using the Think-Pair-Share strategy in learning.	4.7	.517
2.The practice of using Think-Pair-Share was more useful.	4.5	.617
3.I wish my other teachers would use Think-Pair-Share in other subjects too.	4.3	.854
Overall	4.5	.372

Table 5 reveals that participants experienced a high level of enjoyment while using the TPS strategy, as reflected by a mean score of 4.7 (SD = 0.517), indicating an engaging and positive experience. The usefulness of the strategy received an average score of 4.5 (SD = 0.617), suggesting participants found it beneficial. However, a slightly lower mean score of 4.3 (SD = 0.854) for the statement, "I wish my other teachers would use Think-Pair-Share in other subjects," indicated a moderate preference for applying the strategy across other subjects, likely influenced by individual differences.

Overall, participants held favourable views of TPS, with an overall mean score of 4.5 and a low standard deviation of 0.372, reflecting a consistent positive response. These findings are consistent with Sari et al. (2022), who highlighted that TPS increased student engagement and enthusiasm in learning English synonyms, and with Raba (2017), who observed that TPS enriched the learning experience by encouraging proactive participation and improved communication skills.

Table 6

Descriptive statistics for participants' responses in the vocabulary development dimension

Item	M	SD
1. Think-Pair-Share helped me to get better grades on the vocabulary test.	4.4	.561
2. Think-Pair-Share helped me to pronounce words correctly.	4.4	.699
3. Think-Pair-Share helped me to recall and retain the vocabulary items I learned before.	4.4	.822
4. Using Think-Pair-Share helped me to develop my English vocabulary.	4.4	.822
Overall	4.4	.663

Table 6 revealed consistently positive responses across all items, with an overall mean of 4.4 and a moderate standard deviation of 0.663. These findings highlight participants' favourable perceptions of TPS and its effectiveness in improving various aspects of vocabulary acquisition and proficiency.

Table 7.

Descriptive Statistics for the Experimental Group’s Responses in the Communication and Collaboration Dimension

Item	M	SD
1. I have the courage to speak to my mind when I work collaboratively with my classmates.	4.4	.827
2. Think-Pair-Share helped me to listen the opinion of my classmates carefully to reach a better understanding of them.	4.4	.792
3. Think-Pair-Share made me to respect the opinion of my classmates’ .	4.4	.827
Overall	4.4	.549

In the communication and collaboration dimension, participants consistently reported positive experiences, with an overall mean of 4.4 and a standard deviation of 0.594. They demonstrated high confidence in expressing their thoughts during collaborative tasks (M = 4.4, SD = 0.827), indicating that TPS created a supportive environment for open communication. Additionally, participants noted that TPS encouraged active listening and respect for classmates' opinions (M = 4.4), fostering a positive social dynamic in collaborative learning settings.

Table 8.

Descriptive Statistics for the Experimental Group’s Responses in the Academic Performance Dimension

Item	M	SD
1. Think-Pair-Share helped me to understand the text better.	4.7	.69 2
2. Think-Pair-Share helped me to apply grammar easily.	4.6	.66 9
3. Think-Pair-Share helped me to read faster.	4.2	.85 7

4. Think-Pair-Share helped me to speak English more confidently.	4.2	.83	0
5. Think-Pair-Share helped me to develop my writing skills.	4.2	.69	6
6. Think-Pair-Share helped me to develop my listening skills.	4.1	.96	0
Overall	4.3	.56	3

In the academic performance dimension, participants reported consistently positive results with an overall mean of 4.3 ($SD = 0.563$). The strategy excelled in enhancing critical thinking ($M = 4.7$, $SD = 0.692$) and comprehension skills ($M = 4.6$, $SD = 0.669$), while slightly lower scores were observed for listening skills ($M = 4.1$), reading speed ($M = 4.2$), writing skills ($M = 4.2$), and speaking confidence ($M = 4.2$).

Overall, TPS proved to be an effective method for improving English proficiency, offering students opportunities for self-expression, class participation, and discussions, as supported by studies like Elismawati et al. (2021), Raba (2017), and Kaddoura (2013). These studies also emphasized improvements in reading, speaking, and writing skills, as well as critical thinking. Importantly, no participants rated TPS as weak, and the analysis revealed consistently positive perceptions across all dimensions, with slight variations in agreement.

Conclusion

This study explored the effectiveness of the Think-Pair-Share (TPS) strategy on EFL Kerala Reader learners' vocabulary achievement, as well as their perceptions of it during the 2023/2024 academic year. The research involved experimental and control groups, with TPS exclusively implemented in the experimental group. To evaluate the strategy's impact on vocabulary achievement, both groups completed pretests and post-tests, while a questionnaire was administered to gather attitude of student towards TPS.

The findings indicated that the experimental group significantly outperformed the control group in vocabulary achievement. Additionally, students expressed positive attitudes toward TPS, reporting that the strategy contributed to improved test scores, better text comprehension, enhanced pronunciation, vocabulary expansion, and greater confidence in speaking English.

students appreciated how TPS encouraged mutual respect for classmates' opinions, making it both effective and engaging. However, there was some variability in perceptions regarding listening skill improvement, as shown by slightly lower mean scores and higher standard deviations in this area.

Educational Implications

The findings suggest that TPS is a valuable tool for enhancing vocabulary achievement among Kerala readers EFL students. Curriculum developers and policymakers at the SCERT are encouraged to incorporate TPS into eighth-grade English programs. Additionally, teacher training on implementing TPS should be prioritized to maximize its effectiveness and ensure successful application in the classroom.

Limitations and Recommendations for Further Studies

This study focused exclusively on female students, presenting a limitation that future research could address by exploring the effects of TPS in mixed-gender settings. Such studies could provide insights into whether gender dynamics influence group interactions and vocabulary development. Moreover, since this research was limited to eighth-grade students, further studies are recommended across different grade levels to assess the applicability and effectiveness of TPS at various educational stages. Due to research constraints small sample size is selected for the study however the accuracy is maintained by focusing the research questions on the size of the parameter and the researcher collects sufficient data to have an estimate with a desired level of accuracy. Further studies shall be conducted by large sampling to minimise the lack of precision and reliability and to reduce the risk of false conclusions.

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